

Chemically understanding liquid phase synthesis of argyrodite solid electrolyte $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ with highest ionic conductivity for all-solid-state batteries

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ABSTRACT

Solid electrolytes (SEs), which essentially act as both the electron separator and ion conductor, are an important role for all-solid-state lithium-ion batteries. Liquid phase synthesis is one of the promising method due to synthesis SEs due to easy to scale up and lower energy consumption. However, due to the complexity of the SEs prepared by liquid phase synthesis, many problems such as impurity arise, making liquid electrolytes irreplaceable. This study examines and solves why Li_3PO_4 oxide as an impurity is produced upon preparing $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ argyrodite by approaching the chemical factors. This is accomplished by replacing the hydroxide-based solvent with thiol-based solvent through liquid phase synthesis. As a result,

the absence of Li_3PO_4 oxide from the $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ SEs in this study resulted in the $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ attaining the highest ionic conductivity value ($> 2 \text{ mS}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$) ever obtained through liquid-phase synthesis. Furthermore, the absence of Li_3PO_4 in argyrodite SE could magnificently increase the cell's capacity with remarkable stability.

INTRODUCTION

Rechargeable all-solid-state Li-ion batteries (ASSLBs) using non-flammable inorganic solid electrolytes (SEs) show potential for improved safety and increasing power density in comparison with commercialized Li-ion batteries.¹ The development of ASSLBs has been limited by the poor physical contact between the SE and active material and the lack of SE with ionic conductivities at room temperature. Among the inorganic solid electrolytes, sulfide SEs show excellent mechanical properties and relatively high ionic conductivities.^{2,3} One of the most promising materials classes is argyrodite-type $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{X}$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{and I}$).⁴⁻⁹ Argyrodite-type $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{I}$ substituted by Ge^{4+} show a high ionic conductivity of $18 \text{ mS}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$ at room temperature, which is comparable to the current liquid organic electrolyte.¹⁰ Argyrodite-type $\text{Li}_{5.3}\text{PS}_{4.3}\text{Cl}_{1.7}$ was recently found to show a very high ionic conductivity of over $10 \text{ mS}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$ at room temperature.¹¹ Given the lower cost of chloride-based argyrodite-type SE than argyrodite-type SEs with other halide ions, industrial and fundamental battery applications mainly concentrate on this compound.¹²

The commercialization of sulfide-based ASSLBs requires large-scale manufacturing technologies of SEs.¹³ Synthesis of SEs commonly classifies into high-energy mechanical ball milling and liquid-phase synthesis. The high-energy mechanical ball milling causes a serious obstacle to scale-up due to much energy consumption. In contrast, liquid-phase synthesis is more suitable for large-scale manufacturing because of the low-cost and high scalability.¹⁴⁻¹⁶ The wet chemical reaction relies on the nature of organic solvents, which play an important role in the solubility and reactivity of lithium thiophosphates.^{17,18} The argyrodite-type $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$

SEs were synthesized using ethyl diamine, anisole, and ethanol (EtOH) solvents.^{19–24} Ethanol has a high dielectric constant and low boiling point, which facilitates dissolution of argyrodite-type SEs precursor. However, the use of ethanol results in detrimental effects: the forming of Li_3PO_4 and enhancing decomposition kinetics of anion unit in the precursor solution.^{18,24–26} The combination of tetrahydrofuran (THF) and EtOH still leads to the formation of the Li_3PO_4 in argyrodite-type $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ SEs.^{24,26} This highlights that the Li_3PO_4 is produced through an anionic ring-opening reaction of THF in the wet chemical reaction. Taking this into consideration, chloride ion that has stronger nucleophilic in the protic polar solvent than halide anions of Br^- and I^- is not preferred for the liquid-phase synthesis of argyrodite-type SEs without impurities such as Li_3PO_4 . On the other hand, if $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ argyrodite can completely eliminate Li_3PO_4 in the liquid-phase synthesis by using LiCl , it can be adapted to synthesize Li-argyrodite of various compositions. Further, in the non-protic polar solvents such as acetonitrile, acetone, DMF, and DMSO, Lithium cation can be stabilized, however anions are weakly stabilized. Negatively polarized O atom protrudes outside the molecule, so they can approach and stabilize lithium cations.

Herein, we unveil a new wet chemical reaction mechanism of how to eliminate the impurity of Li_3PO_4 in chloride-based argyrodite $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ using acetonitrile (ACN) and 1-propanethiol (PTH). ACN organic solvent resulted in significant reactivity in the Li_2S - P_2S_5 due to its high dielectric constant.¹⁷ The use of PTH excluded the oxygen ion source from EtOH illustrated in Figure 1a and b. PTH could practically remove during the evaporation process because of its low boiling point. X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurement result indicates no Li_3PO_4 crystalline was found on the ACN and PTH solvents for the $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ crystal structure. More importantly, excluding oxide Li_3PO_4 impurity increased the ionic conductivity and stability against the lithium metal from direct current (DC) polarization measurement. The battery performance significantly increased with high capacity retention after several cycles from the exclusion of Li_3PO_4 at the $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ argyrodite crystal structure.

a. Tetrahydrofuran (THF)/ Ethanol (EtOH) or Propanethiol (PTH) mixed solution

b. Acetonitrile (ACN) / PTH mixed solution

Figure 1. Stoichiometry of $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$. The illustration comparison reaction between $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ by liquid-phase synthesis using **a** Tetrahydrofuran (THF) with Ethanol (EtOH) and **b** Acetonitrile (ACN) with 1-Propanethiol (PTH).

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Liquid-phase Synthesis. Reagent for synthesis grade of Li_2S (99.9%, Mitsuwa), P_2S_5 (99%, Merck), and LiCl (99.0%, Sigma-Aldrich) was used as raw materials with the total stoichiometry ratio of 5:1:2 to create $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$. The solution procedure was first separated into two solutions. To begin, we mixed a 3:1 molar ratio of Li_2S and P_2S_5 in 10 ml of THF (anhydrous, 99.9%, Sigma-Aldrich) or ACN (super dehydrated, 99.8%, Fujifilm), and then stirred for 12 h at room temperature or 75 °C, respectively, to form a suspension. Next, the mixture of Li_2S and LiCl with a molar ratio of 2:2 was stirred in 10 ml of EtOH (Super Dehydrated, 99.5%, Fujifilm) at 50 °C or PTH (98%, Tokyo Chemical Industry) at room temperature for 12 h. 3A molecular sieves was added into THF and PTH prior to use in purpose to dehydrate the remaining water content. 100 grams of 3A molecular sieves (around 11.36%

of THF's mass) were added into 1 L of THF with a density of $880 \text{ gram}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$. The same amount was added into the PTH solvent ($880 \text{ gram}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) or 12.20% of PTH's mass. 3 Å molecular sieve was dried at $220 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 18 hours to remove the remaining humidity or water vapor inside the molecular sieves before being poured into each solvent. The resultant suspension and solution were mixed then stirred for 12 h at room temperature (for the ACN + PTH case, $50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). The resulting solution evaporated at $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 12 h under low pressure with a diaphragm pump (Buchi V-700 Vacuum Pump). The evaporated precursor was pelletized for 127 MPa at uniaxial press before the heat treatment process. Argyrodite pellet was heat-treated at various temperatures of $550 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $600 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 and 10 h under an Ar flow. Figure S1 illustrates the liquid-phase synthesis process for ACN + PTH solvents. All processes were performed under a dry Ar atmosphere.

Mechanical Ball Milling Synthesis. Mechanical BM was used to produce $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ and compared with liquid-phase synthesis. Reagents of Li_2S , P_2S_5 , and LiCl were mixed and ground together in an agate mortar for around 15 min. The mixed powder was inserted into a 45 ml zirconia pot and 15 zirconia balls ($\varnothing = 10 \text{ mm}$). The prepared sample was then milled at the rotation of 600 rpm for 20 h using a planetary BM apparatus (Pulverisette 7, Fritsch Co., Ltd.). Thereon, the pulverized powder was then pressed for 127 MPa at uniaxial press before the heat treatment process at $550 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $600 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 and 10 h. All processes were performed under a dry Ar atmosphere.

Material Characterization. The crystal structures of the retrieved samples were investigated using XRD (XRD; SmartLab, Rigaku) with an airtight holder to prevent the samples from being exposed to air humidity. The local structure was investigated using Raman spectroscopy (NRS-3100, Jasco) with the samples sealed inside an Ar-filled glove box. Solid-state ^{31}P magic-angle-spinning NMR (^{31}P -MAS-NMR, Avance III 400, Bruker) was performed using the typical

single pulse sequence with a spinning rate of 6 kHz. Liquid proton ^1H NMR was measured by solving the samples with dimethyl sulfoxide- d_6 (DMSO) using Avance III 400, Bruker. Scanning electron microscope-energy dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (SEM-EDX) images mapping was achieved using Hitachi-S4800 and ULTIM MAX, Oxford Instrument as for the EDX instrument. Thermogravimetry differential thermal analysis TG-DTA (EVO II, Rigaku) was performed under Ar flow with a temperature increase of $5\text{ }^\circ\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ inside glovebox with Ar and dry atmosphere.

Electrochemical Performance Measurement. The temperature dependence of the ionic conductivity of the retrieved sample was investigated using alternating-current impedance spectroscopy (SI 1260, Solartron) from 10 MHz to 1 Hz under dry Ar flow. The samples for impedance measurements were prepared by uniaxial pressing around 80 mg of sample powder into pellets (approximately 10 mm in diameter) under a pressure of 255 MPa for 10 minutes at room temperature. The thickness of the argyrodite SE pellets were approximately reach 0.60 mm. The prepared pellets were placed in a holder made from polyether ether ketone (PEEK) with two blocking electrodes made from stainless steel (SUS). The temperature was increased gradually in a controlled fashion, from room temperature to $150\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ at various increments and held at each temperature for 1 h before the impedance measurement. Electrical conductivity was determined by the DC polarization measurements on the pellets with applied voltages of 0.1, 0.15, 0.2, 0.25, and 0.3 V for 30 min each at room temperature. Lithium metal stability measurement using DC polarization tests by using lithium foils as nonblocking electrodes on both sides of the pelletized SE, then sandwiching them between SUS. The prepared symmetric cells were then cycled at $\pm 0.1\text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ and $\pm 0.2\text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ using a charge-discharge device (BTS-2004H, Nagano) under a dry Ar atmosphere at room temperature. Battery performance for charge and discharge curves were conducted using Li-In alloy as the negative electrode, $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}_{\text{ACN}+\text{PTH}}$ as the electrolyte layer, and $\text{TiS}_2\text{-Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ composite as the positive electrode.

The positive electrodes were fabricated by mixing TiS_2 and SE ($\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$) with the weight ratio of 1:1 on agate mortar with a grind duration of about 15 min. Firstly, SE for about 80 mg was pressed and pelletized at low press into PEEK (inner diameter of 10 mm) with two blocking SUS electrodes. After that, positive electrode powder was kept (~10 mg) at one side of the pelletized SE, then pressed together at 255 MPa uniaxial pressure at room temperature. After Li-In foil was attached to the other side of the pellet sandwich, it was pressed again at 127 MPa uniaxial pressure at room temperature. The cells were cycled using a charge-discharge device (BST-2004H, Nagano) with voltages cutoff in the range of 1.0 to 2.4 V vs. Li-In at 0.1C. All preparations were conducted inside a dry Ar-filled glovebox.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Characterization and ionic conductivity measurement.

Figure 2a presents the commonly used mechanism of the Li_3PO_4 formation by omitting the argyrodite structure. The $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ using THF and EtOH was argyrodite-type structure (Figure 2b). The sample formed the impurity of Li_3PO_4 oxide and the remaining of the Li_2S and LiCl as starting materials. The Li_3PO_4 oxide could be produced by the nucleophilic reaction between anion O^- in the hydroxide from ethanol ($\text{OH}^- \text{Li}^+$) and P_2S_5 , which was created by the reaction of EtOH and LiCl ,²⁷ previously matching other's reported results.^{24,26} This finding suggests that the ethanol solvent gave rise to the oxidation whose reaction changes the hydroxyl bond ($-\text{OH}$) into a thiol bond ($-\text{SH}$). The solvent was replaced with the 1-propanethiol (PTH) in this study. The XRD of the $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ using the mixed solvent of THF and PTH showed argyrodite-type structure with some residual raw material of Li_2S and LiCl and producing the same Li_3PO_4 crystalline. This structural property is a crystalline structure comparable to that of argyrodite SE which uses THF and EtOH-mixed solvents although the solvent system of THF and PTH (Figure 1a) involves no hydroxyl bond. This result indicates that the oxidation formation still occurs via the anionic ring-opening reaction of THF, and the

nucleophilic attack from thiorate anion —S^- of PTH is stronger than that from —O^- anions of EtOH. The anion of Li—X^- may play an important role in THF ring-opening. This was proven from the synthesis of $\beta\text{-Li}_3\text{PS}_4$ using only THF as the solvent and resulted in no Li_3PO_4 oxidation formation.^{28,29} In contrast, the XRD pattern for the sample using the mixed solvent of ACN and PTH showed argyrodite crystalline and a small amount of Li_2S and LiCl without Li_3PO_4 crystalline (Figure 2b), which results in the excluding of Li_3PO_4 from $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ argyrodite SE due to no oxygen source from the system. However, the synthetic mechanism of this oxide was not confirmed in detail. Therefore, we carried out the ^1H NMR spectroscopic studies of Li_3PO_4 oxide formation.

According to this mechanism, as shown in Figure 2a, the EtOH+THF mixed solutions with LiCl in the presence of Li_2S were evaporated at $80\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and examined the ^1H NMR spectra of resulting reaction mixture in DMSO-d_6 , as compared without P_2S_5 and evaporation. TG-DTA curves of $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ precursor prepared using EtOH and THF solvents after evaporated at $80\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ are presented in Figure S2, showing an endothermic peak at $113\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and a weight loss of around 14%. This behavior indicates the evaporation of EtOH+THF solvents. Thus, the remaining solvent in the reaction mixture should remain even after the evaporation at $80\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. As the results of Figure 2c, the NMR spectrum of EtOH+THF mixed solution with LiCl and Li_2S at room temperature resulted in no reaction and interaction. However, after the temperature was promoted from the evaporation process ($80\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$), the chemical shift of methylene protons of THF at 3.63 ppm to the low magnetic field was at 3.77 ppm and showed a broad peak at 2.66 ppm, assigned to the hydroxy group (—OH) in the terminal group of ring-opened THF.³⁰ This data implies the evidence of oxidation from the ring-opening of THF by the negative charge of oxygen (—O^-) in ethanol, probably leading to the weak interaction between H^+ of EtOH and Cl^- of LiCl could be occurred with heating as a driving force. This case was similar to the previous report when THF was stirred with halogen CuBr at $60\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 h, a nucleophilic reaction happened creating a ring opening of THF.³¹ The NMR results

revealed that the ethanol solvent gave rise to the oxidation.

The utilization of PTH under same EtOH+THF condition was conducted to proof the reformation of —O^- anion *via* the anionic ring-opening reaction of THF, and the nucleophilic attack thiolate anion —S^- of PTH is stronger than —O^- anions of EtOH. Figure 2d presents the NMR results from $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ in the mixed solvents of PTH and THF after evaporated at 80 °C, as compared with the PTH+THF mixed solvents in the presence of LiCl and Li_2S . In the PTH solvent with LiCl at room temperature, the ethylene protons neighboring thiol (—SH) was shifted to high magnetic field from 2.47 to 2.43 ppm. In contrast, the chemical shift of the SH group in the PTH+THF mixed solution with LiCl and Li_2S largely shifted from 1.87 to 2.04 ppm due to a stronger interaction of $\text{S}^-\text{H}^+\dots\text{Cl}^-\text{Li}^+$ and with an oxygen in THF ring. Further we observed the NMR spectra from $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ argyrodite prepared with PTH+THF and put the heat to evaporation process at 80 °C. The methylene peak of THF was slightly shift to lower magnetic field, and there is a broad peak of OH around 2.7 ppm from the terminate group of the ring-opened THF, which is almost the same as the ring-opened THF at $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ argyrodite with EtOH+THF.

$\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{ACN-PTH}}$ generated sharper and smaller particles than $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{THF-EtOH}}$, as shown in SEM images (see Figure S3). The presence of the PS_4^{3-} anions structural unit was confirmed by Raman spectroscopy (Figure 2e). $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{ACN-PTH}}$ and $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{BM}}$ showed a broad PS_4^{3-} peak at 420 cm^{-1} . The PS_4^{3-} peak of $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{THF-EtOH}}$ was observed at a lower wave number of 416 cm^{-1} than the other two. This means the incorporation of oxygen ions in the argyrodite system modifies the P – S bond. A higher electronegativity of O relative to Li and S create lattice distortion/disorder, resulting in varied PS bond strengths.³²

Figure S4 a and b shows the Nyquist plots of electrochemical impedance at room temperature and temperature dependence of ionic conductivity from $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{THF + EtOH}}$ and $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{ACN + PTH}}$. These samples exhibited ionic conductivities of 1.57 and 1.68 $\text{mS}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$ at room temperature (25 °C), respectively. The ionic conductivity of Li_3PO_4 was reported to be

10^{-7} – 10^{-6} S cm^{-1} , which is significantly low compared to that of argyrodite (10^{-3} – 10^{-2} S cm^{-1}).³³ The activation energy in Fig. S4 c showed that $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{ACN}} + \text{PTH}$ as the mixed solvents have a lower activation energy of $28.0 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ compared to $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{THF}} + \text{EtOH}$, which has a higher activation energy of $32.0 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$. We demonstrated that increasing the ionic conductivity of $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}$ argyrodite without oxidation from Li_3PO_4 substantiates the ability to employ the liquid-phase synthesis technique. Even a minor quantity of Li_3PO_4 impurity in the SE might limit Li-ion transport and has a significant impact on increasing activation energy.

Figure 2. a The illustration schematic mechanism of the elimination of Li_3PO_4 oxide formation by using acetonitrile (ACN) and 1-propanethiol (PTH) as the solvents. b XRD patterns of $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ prepared by liquid-phase synthesis with THF + EtOH, THF + PTH, and ACN + PTH

as the solvent. All the samples were dried at 80 °C for overnight then heat treated at 600 °C for 2 h. **c, d** ^1H NMR spectra of $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ and $\text{Li}_2\text{S-LiCl}$ with **(c)** THF + EtOH and **(d)** ACN + PTH as the solvents before and after the evaporation process. **e** Raman spectra patterns of $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ with THF + EtOH and ACN + PTH as the solvents and $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ prepared by ball milling.

Heat treatment optimization.

At room temperature, $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{600/\text{ACN} + \text{PTH}/2\text{h}}$ without Li_3PO_4 phase has ionic conductivity almost the same as $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{600/\text{THF} + \text{EtOH}/2\text{h}}$ with Li_3PO_4 phase. The heat treatment temperature and time were optimized to improve the ionic conductivity further. To determine the optimal heat treatment condition for achieving the high ionic conductivity, we measured the TG-DTA from $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{ACN} + \text{PTH}}$ (Figure S5). There are two endothermic peaks at 100 and 185 °C along with the weight decrement of 2% and then 14%, respectively. The endothermic peak at 100 °C indicates the evaporation of the remaining PTH solvent followed by the crystallization of Li_3PS_4 and probably evaporation of the remaining ACN at 185 °C.^{34–36} Starting at 630 °C, there is a small endothermic peak which indicates the release of sulfur content. An exothermic peak at 693 °C signed the argyrodite start to partially decompose until began to fully decompose at 761 °C. This is similar to $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{THF} + \text{EtOH}}$ (Figure S2) which has a small exothermic peak at 659 °C which is the same indication of sulfur releasement. Moreover, $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{THF} + \text{EtOH}}$ began to full degradation at 722 °C. Furthermore, we will focus on the heat treatment time of 10 hours long, according to literature reported by Yu et al. that 550 °C for 10 hours is the optimum heat treatment condition for the argyrodite system.³⁷ Temperature higher than 550 °C will increase the amount of LiCl residual and the precipitation of Li_2S which indicate the degradation, while prolonging the heat treatment time above 10 hours might evaporate the lithium content.^{37,38} This analysis is also supported by the TG-DTA result in Figure S6 from $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{BM}}$ shows a slight exothermic at 600 °C attributed to the degradation of argyrodite into LiCl with the weight decrement around 2-3%.

The release of sulfur was observed at 625 °C with a small endothermic peak which is similar to other argyrodite that was prepared with liquid phase synthesis. The second exothermic peak at 675 °C indicates the argyrodite starts to partially decompose and is followed to start fully decompose at 781 °C along with the 45% weight reduction. Figure 3a shows the XRD patterns of $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{ACN} + \text{PTH}/10\text{h}}$ and $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{THF} + \text{EtOH}/10\text{h}}$ heat treatment at 550 °C and 600 °C. $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{550/\text{THF} + \text{EtOH}/10\text{h}}$ showed the peaks corresponding to Li_2S and LiCl of the starting materials, oxidation of Li_3PO_4 , and the main peak of argyrodite. The peak intensities of residual and oxide increased after the heat treatment temperature at 600 °C for the same amount of time, which indicates that the argyrodite phase starts to degrade at this temperature. The intensity of the Li_3PO_4 oxide increased at 600 °C. This observation indicates that a higher heat temperature encourages Li_3PO_4 development. $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{600/\text{ACN} + \text{PTH}/10\text{h}}$ involved the degradation of the $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ phase with Li_2S and LiCl as the starting material. On the other hand, $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{550/\text{ACN} + \text{PTH}/10\text{h}}$ formed a crystalline of argyrodite with almost an unnoticeable peak of Li_2S .

The $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ with BM technique was used as a reference structure. As shown in Figure S7, the XRD patterns of $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{550/\text{BM}/10\text{h}}$ and $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{600/\text{BM}/10\text{h}}$ showed a crystalline phase of argyrodite-type structure without residual material and, of course, oxidation. There is an obvious peak of Li_2S remaining in the $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{BM}}$ as-synthesized by BM's method. This suggests that the heat treatment process is necessary to obtain a argyrodite crystalline phase with high purity. To study further the local structure of the argyrodite SE, we examined a solid ^{31}P MAS-NMR measurement for $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{ACN} + \text{PTH}}$, $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{THF} + \text{EtOH}}$, and $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{BM}}$. In Fig. 3b, the ^{31}P MAS-NMR spectroscopy of the $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{BM}}$ displays the peak at 88 ppm belonging to PS_4^{3-} anion and the inevitable spinning sidebands. $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ with the mixed solvent of THF and EtOH contains not only the anion of PS_4^{3-} at 88 ppm, but also the chemical shift of PO_4^{3-} anion at 10 ppm.³⁹ This finding proved that EtOH and the oxygen release from the THF ring-opening effect promote the formation of Li_3PO_4 oxide. The

argyrodite with the ACN and PTH mixed solvent involved no oxides, such as Li_3PO_4 , as shown in ^{31}P MAS-NMR spectroscopy. Our study demonstrated that $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ prepared by the liquid-phase method using ACN + PTH have a crystalline and local structure similar to $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ using the BM method, that is highly pure crystal phase without oxides. This led to the study of the industrial-scale production of $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ using the liquid-phase synthesis method.

Investigation of heat treatment condition impact on ionic conductivity for each $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{THF} + \text{EtOH}}$ and $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{ACN} + \text{PTH}}$ sample was conducted by using electrochemical impedance spectroscopy to measure the. Figure 3c shows the Nyquist plots of electrochemical impedance for $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{THF} + \text{EtOH}}$ and $\text{ACN} + \text{PTH}$ heat-treated at $550\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $600\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 10 h, respectively, along with a graph for the temperature dependence of ionic conductivity and the relation with the activation energy from it at Figure S8. The ionic conductivity for $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{550/\text{THF} + \text{EtOH}/10\text{h}}$ was $1.80\text{ mS}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$ at room temperature with an activation energy of $28.3\text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$, whereas the ionic conductivity of $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{600/\text{THF} + \text{EtOH}/10\text{h}}$ decreased to $1.47\text{ mS}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$ with an activation energy of $30.1\text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$. The decrement of the ionic conductivity and the increment of the activation energy was relevant for the XRD patterns result shown in Figure 3a, in which $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{600/\text{THF} + \text{EtOH}}$ partially decomposed into Li_2S and LiCl . The higher temperature at $600\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ induces a higher crystallinity of Li_3PO_4 in $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$, which becomes a factor for decreasing the ionic conductivity at room temperature from the $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{550/\text{THF} + \text{EtOH}}$ sample. In comparison, $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{600/\text{ACN} + \text{PTH}/10\text{h}}$ exhibited ionic conductivity of $2.13\text{ mS}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$ at room temperature and activation energy of $25.2\text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$. Alternatively, the ionic conductivity of $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{550/\text{ACN} + \text{PTH}/10\text{h}}$ increased to $2.75\text{ mS}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$ and the activation energy reduce to $24.8\text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$. When the heat treatment temperature was increased to $600\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the Li_2S crystalline phase was still present, with a minor amount of LiCl crystalline phase appearing as an impurity, whereas the LiCl crystalline phase was not sighted at $550\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{ACN} + \text{PTH}}$ without Li_3PO_4 impurity may cause the degradation of Li_2S and LiCl formation for higher temperature heat treatment. The degrading crystalline phase from

the $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{ACN} + \text{PTH}}$ sample caused a decrease in ionic conductivity. Longer periods of heat treatment is beneficial for achieving the highly crystallized argyrodite-type phase. Taking this into consideration, the heat treatment temperature at 550 °C for 10 h was the optimum for argyrodite in this study as we stated in the previous section.³⁷

For the basic comparison, the ionic conductivity of argyrodites ($\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{550/\text{BM}}$ and $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{600/\text{BM}}$) was prepared with the ball milling method and heat treatment at 550 °C and 600 °C were examined. From Supplementary Figures S9a, b, and c, the Nyquist plot of electrochemical impedance, the temperature dependence of ionic conductivity, and heat treatment temperature dependence of activation energy from both samples was confirmed. The ionic conductivity at room temperature of $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{550/\text{BM}/10\text{h}}$ were $2.90 \text{ mS}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$ with an activation energy of $29.0 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$, while the ionic conductivity of $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/600/\text{BM}/10\text{h}$ at room temperature decreased to $2.20 \text{ mS}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$ and the activation energy was increased to $30.6 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$. The decrease in ionic conductivity resulted from the degradation of the argyrodite crystalline phase. This is also the same as the explanation from argyrodite that prepared with liquid phase synthesis, the increment of heat treatment temperature $> 550 \text{ °C}$ will resulting the degradation of LiCl and precipitation of Li_2S .³⁷ After measuring the ionic conductivity of $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{BM}}$, the ionic conductivity at room temperature and the activation energy from both $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{BM}}$ and $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{ACN} + \text{PTH}}$ liquid-phase synthesis method were compared. Both methods achieved the highest ionic conductivity from this study with heat treatment temperature at 550 °C for 10 h. The Nyquist plots of electrochemical impedance, the temperature dependence of ionic conductivity, and the comparison of activation energy and ionic conductivity were shown in Figures S10a, b, and c. As previously stated, the ionic conductivity of the $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{BM}/550/10\text{h}}$ was $2.90 \text{ mS}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$ at room temperature. At the same time, $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{ACN} + \text{PTH}/550/10\text{h}}$ was $2.75 \text{ mS}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$ for the ionic conductivity at room temperature. The BM method and the subsequent heat treatment allow to create a highly pure crystalline phase of argyrodite without any residual trace. $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{BM}}$ has a higher ionic

conductivity at room temperature than $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{ACN} + \text{PTH}}$, which corresponds to the small amount of Li_2S residual materials in $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{BM}}$. The SEM image of $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{BM}}$ itself in Figure S11 shows that the morphology of the SE is bulkier than $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{ACN} + \text{PTH}}$ (Figure S3). However, the activation energy of $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{ACN} + \text{PTH}}$ ($24.8 \text{ kJ} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$) has the upper hand due to the lower value of the activation energy compared to the $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{BM}}$ ($29.0 \text{ kJ} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$). Furthermore, the crystallite size comparison from each $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{BM}}$, $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{ACN} + \text{PTH}}$, and $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{THF} + \text{EtOH}}$ could be found in supplementary Table S1 by using the Debye-Scherrer equation.⁴⁰ The smallest average crystallite size could be get from $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{THF} + \text{EtOH}}$ at 102 nm, then followed by $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{ACN} + \text{PTH}}$ with 136 nm. The largest average crystallite size could be attributed to $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{BM}}$ which is 139 nm. The larger the crystallite size response to higher the ionic conductivity results, however, the correlation between crystallite size and conductivity from the argyrodite system requires further analysis.³⁷ Eventually, the ionic conductivity difference at room temperature was insignificant and comparable for both $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{BM}}$ and $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{ACN} + \text{PTH}}$.

Figure 3. **a** XRD patterns of $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ prepared by liquid-phase synthesis with THF + EtOH and ACN + PTH solvents. All the samples were dried at 80 °C overnight then heat-treated at 550 °C and 600 °C for 10 h. **b** ^{31}P MAS-NMR results from $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ prepared by ball milling and liquid-phase methods with different types of solvent from THF + EtOH and ACN + PTH after the heat treatment processes. **c** Nyquist plots of electrochemical impedance at room temperature from $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ with THF + EtOH and ACN + PTH as the solvents after dried and heat-treated at 550 °C and 600 °C for 10 h.

Lithium Metal Stability and Battery Performance Measurement.

Electrochemical performance measurements from DC polarization galvanostatic and battery performance tests were performed to further understand the role of the Li_3PO_4 exclusion for the argyrodite $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}$. Here we demonstrated the symmetrical lithium cell from $\text{Li} | \text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_m | \text{Li}$ ($m = \text{BM}, \text{THF} + \text{EtOH}, \text{ACN} + \text{PTH}$) with the current density of $0.1 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ for the first 100 cycles (200 h) and increase to $0.2 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ starting from the 101st cycle at room temperature. Figure 4a shows the voltage profiles from the lithium metal stability measurement. $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{BM}$ had an initial overpotential of 6 mV without detectable overpotential alterations until 10 h. The overpotential was suddenly dropped to 0 mV (inset 2 mV from Figure 4a), which indicates a short circuit caused by the lithium dendrite already reaching the opposite side of the electrode. The stability was extremely poor despite $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{BM}$ having the highest ionic conductivity without any Li_3PO_4 oxide formation. This result is similar to the sulfide SEs that was prepared by mechanical ball milling that was reported by Li Y et.al and Gamo H. et.al.^{15,41} There are many reasons for the lithium dendrite to grow: low ion transport, high electronic conductivity, and poor mechanical property of SEs.^{42–44} Electronic conductivity for each type SEs are shown in Figure S12. $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{BM}}$, $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{THF} + \text{EtOH}}$, and $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{ACN} + \text{PTH}}$ exhibited electron conductivities of $2.25 \times 10^{-9} \text{ S}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$, $7 \times 10^{-7} \text{ S}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$, and $4.35 \times 10^{-9} \text{ S}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$, respectively. $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{THF} + \text{EtOH}}$ owned the highest electronic conductivity among the others, which supports the reason $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{THF} + \text{EtOH}}$ was unstable against lithium metal and the potential was gradually increased during lithium metal stability measurement. On contrary, $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{ACN} + \text{PTH}}$ has an electron conductivity around 100 times lower than $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{THF} + \text{EtOH}}$ and therefore the increment of the potential is also lower, which makes $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{ACN} + \text{PTH}/550/10\text{h}}$ has better lithium metal stability compared to $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{THF} + \text{EtOH}}$. $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{BM}}$ has the lowest electron conductivity compared to the other two that were prepared with liquid phase synthesis, but the higher crystallinity phase might cause a lower contact area between SE and lithium metal electrodes, leading to lower interfacial combability.⁴³ In the case of $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{THF} + \text{EtOH}}$, the voltage

profile at the initial period showed unstable overpotential between 5 and 21 mV in stripping and plating. This indicates that the thickness of the Solid Electrolyte Interface (SEI) was different, which may result from the existence of the Li_3PO_4 crystalline phase that blocks the path for Li^+ ion movement. Inset 3 in Figure 4a shows that after 200 h, the cycling of $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{THF} + \text{EtOH}}$ revealed a violent increment of the overpotential from 21 to 154 mV (~630% of overpotential increment). Although the SE was not short-circuited, the overpotential dramatically increased because of the production of a layer of resistive passivation. The overpotential increment got worse when the current density increased to $0.2 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$, where the SE was already broken in this state. Our previous study regarding the addition of oxide compound of Li_3PO_4 into $\text{Li}_7\text{P}_2\text{S}_8\text{I}$ (LPSI) using liquid-phase shaking method resulted in magnificent lithium metal stability compared to pristine LPSI.⁴⁵ This result was not consistent with $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{THF} + \text{EtOH}}$, which contains Li_3PO_4 .⁴⁵ The LPSI doped with Li_3PO_4 involves an oxysulfide bond compound from PO_xS_y , which causes the SE to have high lithium metal stability. In the instance of $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{THF} + \text{EtOH}}$, Li_3PO_4 was produced through a nucleophilic reaction that did not create chemical bonds with the argyrodite itself, as seen in the ^{31}P MAS-NMR result. There is no oxysulfide bond formed, simply the bond between PS_4^{3-} and PO_4^{3-} .⁴⁵

$\text{Li} \mid \text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{ACN} + \text{PTH}} \mid \text{Li}$ symmetric cell showed identical overpotential profiles at 6 mV at the initial stage. The alterations of the overpotential were insignificantly increased to 13 mV (~117% of overpotential increment) at the end of the $0.1 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ current density (after 200 h). When the measurement continues to a higher current density of $0.2 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$, the overpotential of the symmetric cell using $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{ACN} + \text{PTH}}$ increased up to 26 mV. As the measurement continues at $0.2 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ of the current density, the SE could maintain its overpotential without any alteration for the next 47 h. The overpotential was dropped to 15 mV, which indicates the lithium dendrites have already grown and penetrated the interface of $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{ACN} + \text{PTH}}$. In sum, $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{ACN} + \text{PTH}}$ exhibits magnificent lithium metal stability compared to $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{THF} + \text{EtOH}}$ because of no impurity of the Li_3PO_4 in $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{ACN} +$

PTH.

To understand the efficacy of the argyrodite prepared for this study and the effect of the Li_3PO_4 impurity on it, a Li–In | $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{ACN} + \text{PTH}}$ | $\text{TiS}_2\text{-Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ m ($m = \text{THF} + \text{EtOH}$, $\text{ACN} + \text{PTH}$) half-cell was assembled then measured, using $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{ACN} + \text{PTH}}$ as the electrolyte layer. The use of Li–In alloy as the negative electrode material benefits the interface stability and mechanical properties compared to intrinsic Li metal. This measurement focuses on $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ performance and the difference between the presence and absence of the Li_3PO_4 impurity in $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$. Figure 4b shows the charge and discharge capacity curve cycled under a cycle rate of 0.1 C at room temperature. $\text{TiS}_2\text{-Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{THF} + \text{EtOH}}$ composite exhibited the initial discharge capacity at $197.68 \text{ mAh}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ and initial charge capacity of $182.8 \text{ mAh}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$, while $\text{TiS}_2\text{-Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{ACN} + \text{PTH}}$ composite exhibited the initial discharge and charge capacity at 222.4 and $221.7 \text{ mAh}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$, respectively. The discharge and charge capacity from the $\text{TiS}_2\text{-Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{ACN} + \text{PTH}}$ composite was superior to the $\text{TiS}_2\text{-Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{THF} + \text{EtOH}}$ composite, which can be explained by the existence of insulating Li_3PO_4 in the SEs. Supplementary Figure S13a and b show the cycling performance and Coulombic efficiency from both samples up to 30 cycles. $\text{TiS}_2\text{-Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{THF} + \text{EtOH}}$ composite showed the discharge capacity of only $87 \text{ mAh}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ with the Coulombic efficiency at 98.4% at the 30th cycle. This implies a discharge capacity retention rate of around 44% from the beginning to the 30th cycle. In contrast, the $\text{TiS}_2\text{-Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{ACN} + \text{PTH}}$ composite discharge capacity at the 30th cycle reached $148.7 \text{ mAh}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ with the Coulombic efficiency of 95%. It had a higher capacity retention rate of approximately 67% compared to the $\text{TiS}_2\text{-Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{THF} + \text{EtOH}}$ composite. The presence of the Li_3PO_4 results in lower contact between the electrode and SE and hinders the path of the Li^+ ions. As a result, the $\text{TiS}_2\text{-Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{THF} + \text{EtOH}}$ composite containing Li_3PO_4 showed a lower initial discharge capacity and lower capacity retention rate than $\text{TiS}_2\text{-Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{ACN} + \text{PTH}}$ composite. In contrast, the Coulombic efficiency of $\text{TiS}_2\text{-Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{ACN} + \text{PTH}}$ composite (95%) is lower than that of $\text{TiS}_2\text{-Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}/\text{SE}_{\text{THF} + \text{EtOH}}$ composite (98.4%). This phenomenon may be described by

the decomposition reaction at the interface between TiS_2 and SEs. TiS_2 has the electrochemical window range at 0.9-2.8 V while $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ argyrodite stable electrochemical operating window at 1.70-2.01 V.^{46,47} The great difference between electrochemical window between TiS_2 and $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ may cause decomposition reaction in the interface between them. We believe that $\text{TiS}_2\text{-Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl/SE}_{\text{ACN} + \text{PTH}}$ composite involves intimate contact at the interface due to the absence of Li_3PO_4 , which causes a severe decomposition reaction.⁴⁸ SEM-EDX mapping from the positive active material composites with the corresponding Ti, Cl, S, and P elements from both $\text{TiS}_2\text{-Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl/SE}_{\text{THF} + \text{EtOH}}$ composite (Figure 4c, d, e, f, and g) and $\text{TiS}_2\text{-Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl/SE}_{\text{ACN} + \text{PTH}}$ composite (Figure 4h, i, j, k, and l) were determined. The absence of the sulfur and titanium elements was observed in part of the $\text{TiS}_2\text{-Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl/SE}_{\text{THF} + \text{EtOH}}$ composite particles, whereas the phosphorus element was slightly concentrated in that region shown in Figure 4d and f. This experimental result indicates that this region was the existence of the Li_3PO_4 , which was consistent with the XRD and NMR results. The agglomeration of the Li_3PO_4 from the SEM-EDX mapping also corresponds to the unidentical overpotential profile from $\text{TiS}_2\text{-Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl/SE}_{\text{THF} + \text{EtOH}}$ using the galvanostatic DC polarization measurement. The distribution of the chlorine element originating from the argyrodite phase was homogeneous. SEM-EDX mapping of $\text{TiS}_2\text{-Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl/SE}_{\text{ACN} + \text{PTH}}$ composite showed particle morphology with no concentrated phosphorus element and sulfur atom, indicating the absence of a Li_3PO_4 phase from the composite structure and the SE. Our discovery on the mechanism and exclusion of Li_3PO_4 from $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl/SE}$ argyrodite systems prepared using liquid-phase synthesis will significantly contribute to fundamental scientific research from the chemical aspect of the ASSLiBs development. Therefore, we believe this finding will pave the way for the future engineering of energy storage devices.

Figure 4. **a** Galvanostatic DC polarization of symmetrical cell from $\text{Li} | \text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl } m | \text{Li}$ ($m = \text{BM}, \text{THF} + \text{EtOH}, \text{ACN} + \text{PTH}$) at room temperature with 1 h for each charge and discharge. **b** Charge and discharge capacity curve for $\text{Li-In} | \text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl} \text{ ACN} + \text{PTH} | \text{TiS}_2\text{-Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl } m$ ($m = \text{THF} + \text{EtOH}, \text{ACN} + \text{PTH}$) at room temperature with 0.1C rate. **c** Temperature dependence of ionic conductivity from $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ with THF + EtOH and ACN + PTH as the solvents after dried and heat-treated at 550 °C and 600 °C for 10 h. **c, d, e, f, g** SEM-EDX mappings from $\text{TiS}_2\text{-Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ THF + EtOH composite of Ti, Cl, S, and P elements for the selected regions. **h, i, j, k, l** SEM-EDX mappings from $\text{TiS}_2\text{-Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ ACN + PTH composite of Ti, Cl, S, and P elements for the selected regions.

CONCLUSIONS

In summary, we demonstrated promising solvents and methods for the scalable liquid phase synthesis of $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ argyrodite solid electrolyte with no impurity of Li_3PO_4 impurity was formed on the structure, showing the enhanced ionic conductivity, Li metal anode stability, and battery cycle performance. The hydroxyl bond from the EtOH and anionic reaction from THF's ring-opening effect from Li-X^- nucleophilic attack were successfully excluded by using ACN and PTH as the solvents. The use of ACN and PTH allows to synthesize $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ argyrodite without any Li_3PO_4 impurity, which is observed from the XRD and the ^{31}P MAS-NMR results. The ionic conductivity of $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ without Li_3PO_4 increased from that of the sample with Li_3PO_4 because of the absence of the huge resistance from Li_3PO_4 . Moreover, $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ without Li_3PO_4 showed a better Li dendrite growth suppression compared with $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ containing Li_3PO_4 impurity. Our synthetic method of Li- argyrodite designed by understanding chemistry declared a best condition in the liquid phase synthesis. Therefore, it would be adaptable to the liquid-phase synthesis of sulfur-containing Li-argyrodite of various compositions due to higher nucleophilicity of LiCl than that of lithium bromide (LiBr) and lithium iodide (LiI). Regarding the battery performance, we found the increment of the charge and discharge capacity and more stable cycle performance owned to $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ without any Li_3PO_4 impurity on it. The high Li-anode stability and the improved battery cycle performance from the $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ could happen due to no other than the exclusion of the impurity Li_3PO_4 which resulting higher ionic conductivity. The design of the chemical factor's solvent selection for the preferable liquid phase synthesis without any impurity could discover a feasible path for applicable high electrochemical performance battery with high stability against either Li-anode or cathode with the possibility of mass production.

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NOTES

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information.

The Supporting Information is available free of charge at

Structural information obtained from schematic illustration, TG-DTA curves, X-ray Diffraction data, Nyquist plot of temperature dependence, temperature dependence of ionic conductivity, activation energy, electronic conductivity data, charge and discharge curve, images from scanning electron microscope, and table for Scherrer data.

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Author Contributions

R.F.I. conceived, conducted the experimental work, analyzed, and wrote the paper. H.G. conceived, conducted the experimental work, analyzed, review, and editing. A.N. conceived, analyzed, review, editing, and supervised the study and work. A.M. raised the funds, analyzed, review, editing, and supervised the study and work.

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